

Supplemental figure 1

Mouse and rabbit antibodies:

- 1: ETV6 ab54705 and RUNX1 ab23980
- 2: ETV6 sc166835 and RUNX1 ab23980
- ▲ 3: RUNX1 ab110035 and ETV6 sc11382